

2 **Controlled feeding experiments with diets of different abrasiveness reveal slow**
3 **development of mesowear signal in goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*).**

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16 **KEY WORDS: Mesowear, Grit, Tooth wear, Controlled food trials, Ruminant**

17

18 **Summary statement**

19 Controlled feeding experiment in goats shows that the mesowear signal represents a stable
20 dietary period longer than six months.

21

22 **List of Symbols and Abbreviations used**

23 CT: Computer tomography

24 CS: Cusp shape

25 CSA: Cusp shape of the anterior cusp

26 CSP: Cusp shape of the posterior cusp

27 OR: Occlusal relief

28 L: Lucerne diet

29 G: Grass diet

30 GR: Grass-rice husk diet

31 GRS: Grass-rice husk-sand diet

32 ADIA: Acid-detergent insoluble ash

33 M1-3: Upper molar

34 m1-3: Lower molar

35 P2-4: Upper premolar

36 p2-4: Lower premolar

37

38 **ABSTRACT**

39 Dental mesowear is applied as a proxy to determine the general diet of mammalian
40 herbivores based on tooth-cusp shape and occlusal relief. Low, blunt cusps are considered
41 typical for grazers and high, sharp cusps typical for browsers. However, how internal or
42 external abrasives impact mesowear, and the time frame the wear signature takes to develop,
43 still need to be explored. Four different pelleted diets of increasing abrasiveness (lucerne,
44 grass, grass and rice husks, grass, rice husks and sand) were fed to four groups of a total of 28
45 adult goats in a controlled feeding experiment over a six-month period. Tooth morphology
46 was captured by medical CT scans at the beginning and end of the experiment. These scans,
47 as well as the crania obtained postmortem, were scored using the mesowear method.
48 Comparisons between diet groups only showed few significant differences after six months,
49 irrespective of whether CT scans or the real teeth were scored. Only when assessing the
50 difference in signal between start and end did relevant, significant diet-specific effects
51 emerge. Diets containing lower phytolith content caused a more pronounced change in
52 mesowear towards sharper cusps/higher reliefs, while the feed containing sand did not result
53 in more extreme changes in mesowear when compared to the same feed without sand. Our
54 experiment suggests that the formation of a stable and hence reliable mesowear signal
55 requires more time to develop than six months.

56

57 INTRODUCTION

58 In 2000, Fortelius and Solounias introduced mesowear analysis; a method to rapidly
59 reconstruct paleodiets based on macroscopic attritive and abrasive wear on the molars of
60 ungulate herbivores by observing cheek-tooth occlusal surfaces. As a result, herbivores can
61 quickly be classified as browsers or grazers by observation of their mesowear profile, defined
62 by each tooth's cusp shape (CS) and occlusal relief (OR). The concept of mesowear suggests
63 that tooth-on-tooth wear, or attrition, creates teeth with sharp, pointed cusps and high
64 occlusal relief, which is characteristic of a browser, as their diet is hardly abrasive. For
65 grazers, in contrast, the concept suggests that their teeth are mainly worn down by an
66 abrasive diet, in which plant phytoliths and/or external abrasives such as grit and dust grind
67 down the dental material, resulting in lower occlusal relief and blunter cusps (Fortelius and
68 Solounias, 2000; Kaiser, 2000).

69 In the original mesowear scoring system, only the upper second molar was used, and
70 CS was scored as sharp, round or blunt and OR as high or low (Fortelius and Solounias,
71 2000; Kaiser, 2000). Since then, the system was expanded to include upper and lower molars
72 (Franz-Odenaal and Kaiser, 2003; Kaiser and Fortelius, 2003; Kaiser and Solounias, 2003),
73 as well as a higher number of differentiated scoring states (e.g. Winkler and Kaiser, 2011).
74 On the other hand, a more simplified version of the scoring system using a set of gauges has
75 also been introduced (Mihlbachler et al., 2011). Due to species- or taxon-specific adaptations
76 and exceptions, various modified mesowear scoring systems have been developed for equids
77 (Kaiser and Fortelius, 2003), lagomorphs (Fraser and Theodor, 2010), rhinoceroses (Taylor et
78 al., 2013), marsupials (Butler et al., 2014), and small mammals (Kropacheva et al., 2017;
79 Ulbricht et al., 2015). Mesowear has also been applied to fossil taxonomic lineages such as
80 chalicotheriidae (Schulz et al., 2007) and notoungulates (Croft and Weinstein, 2008), and in
81 some cases alternative scoring systems using angles and gauges have been used for taxa such
82 as proboscideans (Saarinen et al., 2015) and xenarthrans (Saarinen and Karme, 2017). Due to
83 the array of varying mesowear techniques, caution should be applied referring to the
84 methodology of the respective mesowear studies, especially when comparing data from
85 different publications.

86 In extant ungulates mesowear is most commonly used to reconstruct paleodiets and
87 paleoecology (Croft and Weinstein, 2008), under the assumption that the wear pattern
88 *"generally reflects a substantial portion of the individual's life in ecological time"* (Fortelius
89 and Solounias, 2000). Very young and senile individuals are generally excluded from
90 mesowear databases, as their extreme signal is not representative of the general population.
91 The macroscopically visible wear pattern is a guide to answer questions about the average

92 diet of a specific species from a particular location. It has also been used to demonstrate tooth
93 wear variability within a species, when different diets are consumed due to various factors
94 such as climate variables, seasonality, population-specific habitat differences or sexual
95 segregation (Clauss et al., 2007; Kaiser et al., 2009; Kaiser and Schulz, 2006; Schulz et al.,
96 2007; Taylor et al., 2016; Taylor et al., 2014; Winkler and Kaiser, 2011; Yamada, 2012).
97 However, it should be noted that the studies mentioned above only made assumptions about
98 diet composition under the respective circumstances such as 'the wild' or 'captivity', or
99 referred to the literature. Only very few studies correlate actual feeding observations with
100 mesowear signals in individuals of the observed populations (Schulz et al., 2013; Wronski
101 and Schulz-Kornas, 2015). Up to this date, a single study (Solounias et al., 2014) has
102 measured mesowear based on a controlled experimental diet, and in this case a new scoring
103 system was introduced, called 'mesowear III' (with the terms 'mesowear I' describing the
104 Kaiser and Solounias (2003) method scoring more than one cusp per tooth, and the term
105 'mesowear II' referring to the scoring system of Mihlbachler and Solounias (2006)). For
106 mesowear III, the shape of the inner enamel bands of molars is scored on both their occlusal-
107 mesial and their distal side. Original mesowear scoring was not applied in that experiment,
108 possibly because the relatively short experimental period (up to 40 days) may not have been
109 long enough for a 'mesowear I or II' signal to develop (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000).
110 Correspondingly, Danowitz et al. (2016) claim that 'mesowear III', designated 'inner
111 mesowear', develops faster than the original or 'outer mesowear'.

112 The mesowear signal changes with age within a species and at different rates across
113 species (Rivals et al., 2007). However, the length of time this signal takes to develop has not
114 been investigated thus far. Most likely, this period is short in lagomorphs and rodents, where
115 a reliable signal can be obtained (Fraser and Theodor, 2010; Ulbricht et al., 2015) even
116 though the cheek tooth crowns are completely replaced within 1-2 weeks (Müller et al., 2014;
117 Müller et al., 2015).

118 In order to test whether, and at which rate, a controlled diet can induce mesowear
119 changes, goats were provided with diets of varying abrasiveness for a period of six months.
120 We expected individuals fed with a phytolith-poor diet to develop a high-sharp mesowear
121 signal and individuals on a phytolith-rich diet to develop a low-round to blunt mesowear
122 signal. An even more drastic effect was anticipated when the same diets were used with
123 added external abrasives. The change in macroscopic tooth shape was recorded using
124 computed-tomographic (CT) imaging and mesowear scoring of CT scans at the beginning
125 and the end of the experimental period.

126

127 MATERIALS AND METHODS

128 Animals

129 The animal experiments were performed with approval of the Swiss Cantonal Animal Care
130 and Use Committee Zurich (animal experiment license N° 115/2009). Twenty-eight adult
131 female domestic goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*, Linnaeus 1758) of mixed breeds and varying
132 ages (Saanen goats, Chamois Colored goats and Toggenburger goats; average body mass =
133 60 ± 8 kg, estimated age = 3-10 years, exact ages unknown), with unknown previous feeding
134 history, were randomly divided into four groups, each consisting of seven individuals, and
135 kept in a stable with an indoor compartment (40 m² per group) consisting of a slatted
136 concrete floor, an area covered by industrial carpet, and an outdoor compartment (12 m² per
137 group) with a concrete floor. The duration of the feeding experiment ranged from 182 to 198
138 days for 24 animals and from 107 to 176 days for four other animals that were euthanized
139 before the end of the experiment due to reasons unrelated to the study (see supplementary
140 information for details on individual animals). At the end of the experimental period the
141 animals were slaughtered and the skulls were prepared by enzymatic maceration at the Center
142 of Natural History, University of Hamburg, where they are permanently curated in the
143 Mammals Collection.

144

145 Diets

146 All animals were fed lucerne hay and lucerne pellets for *ad libitum* consumption during two
147 weeks before the first CT and the start of the experimental diet feeding period. The
148 experimental diets differed in abrasiveness between the groups, with increasing abrasiveness
149 from lucerne pellets (L), grass pellets (G) to grass pellets with rice husks (GR) and grass
150 pellets with rice husks with an addition of sand (GRS; Sand for playgrounds, grain size 0–1
151 mm, REDSUN garden products B.V., Heijen, Denmark; mean particle size measured by
152 sieve analysis of 0.233 mm). These diets were of the same batch as those used in experiments
153 with rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) (Müller et al., 2014), guinea pigs (*Cavia porcellus*)
154 (Müller et al., 2015) and *in vitro* with horse teeth (Karme et al., 2016). During the production
155 of the pelleted diets, care was taken to ensure that the proportion of indigestible abrasives in
156 the GRS diet was mimicked in the other diets by a similar proportion of indigestible, non-
157 abrasive filler, to ensure comparable levels of energy and nutrients per amount of pellets
158 (Müller et al., 2014). Grass hay was provided to all groups except for the lucerne group,
159 which was fed lucerne hay. 1500 g of pelleted food and 100 g of hay was provided daily per
160 animal. It should be noted that in this experiment the diets were designed to mainly comprise
161 pellets, and the provided proportion of hay was therefore lower than the normal forage ration

162 for ruminants. Water was available for *ad libitum* consumption at all times. Samples of all
163 diet items, as well as faeces of all animals, were analysed for acid-detergent insoluble ash
164 (ADIA) as a measure for silica (abrasives) content (Hummel et al., 2011); a nutritional
165 analysis of the pelleted diets is given in Müller et al. (2014). Diet samples represented a
166 composite sample of each hay and pellet type, blended from individual weekly samples;
167 faecal samples of all animals were collected immediately before slaughter, *i.e.* after the
168 animals had been on their respective diets for six months.

169

170 **Computer tomography**

171 Computed tomography images were acquired from a helical multislice Siemens scanner
172 (Siemens Medical Solutions, Erlangen, Germany) housed at University of Zurich Tierspital.
173 The parameters kept constant throughout were: tube voltage at 120 kVp, image matrix of 512
174 x 512 pixels, field of view 980 x 332 pixels, slice thickness of 0.6 mm and B60s convolution
175 kernel. The animals were scanned at the start of the experiment, while they were in groups
176 but not yet on experimental diets. The scans took place under general anesthesia with
177 Ketamin 10 mg/kg (Ketonarkon[®], Streuli Pharma AG, Uznach, Switzerland) and Xylazin 0.1
178 mg/kg (Xylazin Streuli, Streuli Pharma AG, Uznach, Switzerland) intramuscularly.
179 Anesthesia was maintained with isoflurane (Attane[®], Provet AG, Lyssach, Switzerland)
180 administered in oxygen using a facemask. The first CT scan was used as baseline for the
181 tooth condition. Another CT scan was performed post-mortem.

182

183 **Mesowear**

184 The goats' skulls were scored in two ways: first physically by inspection of the original skull
185 material, with aid of a magnifying lens (magnification x12) and second virtually using the
186 rendered 3D surface model of the CT data. Mesowear was scored on all premolars and
187 molars excluding unworn, extremely worn or otherwise damaged specimens (Kaiser et al.,
188 2009) using the mesowear scoring protocol from Taylor et al. (2013) and Taylor et al. (2016)
189 adapted from Fortelius and Solounias (2000) and Winkler and Kaiser (2011). In this system,
190 tooth cusp shape (CS) of the anterior (CSA) and the posterior molar cusp (CSP) can be
191 scored as sharp (CS 4), round-sharp (CS 3), round (CS 2), round-round (CS 1) and blunt (CS
192 0). Occlusal relief (OR) was scored by observing the proportion between height and width of
193 the anterior and posterior molar tooth cusps. Based on this, the different scores are high-high
194 (OR 4), high (OR 3), high-low (OR 2), low (OR 1), and flat-negative (OR 0). This scoring
195 system is not species-specific and is suitable for application on ruminants. Because it was our
196 aim to develop a functional understanding, we investigated diet effects of the individual

197 mesowear components (cusp shape and occlusal relief) separately, and did not report results
198 from a combined score (where CS and OR scores are combined into a single number, *e.g.*
199 Kaiser et al., 2009; Winkler and Kaiser, 2011) here. To conform with the way mesowear was
200 scored in our experiment, the combined score values are reversed from the continuous system
201 as presented in Winkler and Kaiser (2011), with 0 being the bluntest lowest score and 17
202 being the sharpest and highest score. A corresponding evaluation is provided in the
203 supplementary information.

204

205 The CT datasets were converted to DICOM medical imaging format and rendered into
206 3D surface models using Amira 5.6 (Mercury Computer Systems/3D Viz group, San Diego,
207 CA) as well as Horos v3.0.1 (Horos Project 2015) for additional visualisation. To allow for
208 mesowear scoring in Amira, view mode was set to orthographic mode and a fixed iso-surface
209 threshold was defined such as to achieve the highest bone resolution while avoiding artefacts.
210 Mesowear scoring of the CT images was performed using a dynamic 3D model of the data; in
211 other words, there was no pre-set, fixed on-screen magnification. Apart from the individual
212 scores, the score difference between the skull and final CT scan was calculated, as well as the
213 score difference between the initial and the final CT scans for each cusp/tooth. All mesowear
214 scoring was performed blinded to diet groups, and the scoring of the skulls was performed
215 separately from that of the CT scans. All scoring was performed by the same investigator
216 (NLA), and the descriptive scores (*e.g.* high, blunt, sharp; summarized in the supplementary
217 information) were transferred into numerical values as described above. The difference in
218 scores taken from skulls and CT scans was not used to adjust scoring, but were part of this
219 investigation.

220

221 **Statistical analysis**

222 For statistical analysis, data for left and right teeth were entered separately in the dataset.
223 Overall difference in sharpness between anterior and posterior cusps was tested, as well as
224 the differences between mesowear results from the same time point using different methods
225 (virtually on CT scans and physically on skulls). Comparisons within individuals (such as
226 between anterior and posterior cusps, between the initial and final CT scans, and between the
227 CT and the skull scores) were made by Wilcoxon signed-rank tests for paired samples. The
228 distributions of differences between CT and skull scores were assessed by median, mean,
229 skewness and kurtosis. Comparisons between treatment groups were performed using ranked
230 data and General Linear Models with Tukey's post hoc tests; data were ranked every time
231 anew corresponding to the level of analysis (all teeth, all premolars/molars, all upper

232 premolars/molars and all lower premolars/molars, and each individual tooth position) and
233 compared between the four groups. Comparisons of fecal ADIA levels were made using the
234 original data and an ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test. Correlations between scores were
235 assessed by Spearman's ρ . All analyses were performed in SPSS 22.0 (IBM, Armonk, NY,
236 USA), with the significance level set to $P < 0.05$. Although most analyses were non-
237 parametric (incl. the use of ranked data), graphs are based on means and standard deviations
238 to allow visual interpretation of differences.

239

240 **RESULTS**

241 **Dietary silica content**

242 The ADIA content of lucerne and grass hay was very similar to that of the pelleted diets
243 made from each respective material (Fig. 1A). As intended, the diet including rice husks had
244 a higher ADIA concentration and the diet with added sand had a very high ADIA
245 concentration of 92.8 g per kg of dry matter. The fecal ADIA levels differed significantly
246 between the groups (ANOVA $p < 0.001$, Fig. 1B), with a significant difference at post hoc-
247 testing between the GRS and the other groups ($p < 0.001$ in all cases) and no overlap in the
248 95% confidence intervals of any group means.

249

250 **Mesowear scores on skulls**

251 At the end of the experiment, mesowear scores performed on skulls and averaged across all
252 molars show the lucerne diet group as having higher OR scores compared to the other diet
253 groups. The GRS diet group generally had significantly lower CS scores than the L group,
254 with other diet groups in varying positions according to the level of analysis (Fig. 2; Table 1).
255 Combining the OR and CS scores into a single variable for measurements performed on
256 skulls, CT1, CT2 and the difference between CT1 and CT2 resulted in equal or less
257 differentiation between the diet groups of our experiments, but in no case in a higher level of
258 differentiation (Tables S1-S3, Fig. S1).

259

260 **Physical and digital scoring**

261 Comparing mesowear scores from post-mortem CT scans and skulls, the percentage of score
262 differences for the OR parameter resembled a normal distribution (albeit with positive
263 kurtosis) around zero, indicating no systematic discrepancy between skull and CT OR scores
264 (Fig. 3). Both CS score differences showed a similar (less kurtotic) distribution shifted (but
265 not skewed) towards the right (Fig. 3). Statistically, no difference was found between the
266 skull and CT scoring for OR (Table 2), and the two measures were significantly correlated

267 (p<0.001 for all teeth as well as premolars and molars separately; $\rho=0.44$ for all teeth and
268 premolars and 0.25 for molars). However, CS scores differed significantly in the overall
269 comparison and in each sub-category, as well as for several individual teeth, with cusps being
270 scored as sharper on average in the physical skulls than in the CT scans (Table 2).
271 Nevertheless, for CSA (premolars: p<0.001, $\rho=0.28$; molars p=0.004, $\rho=0.18$) and CSP
272 (molars: p=0.005, $\rho=0.17$) skull and CT data were significantly correlated as well. The diet
273 did not have a systematic effect on the difference between skull and CT scores (Table 2).

274

275 **Sharpness of anterior vs. posterior cusps**

276 Whether the physical skull or CT scans were scored had an effect on the difference in the
277 perceived sharpness between anterior and posterior cusps. No differences between anterior
278 and posterior cusps in CS scores were found for scores performed on the skulls (Table S4).
279 For those performed virtually on the CT scans, cusp scores differed significantly in many
280 cases, and nearly in all molars for the second CT scan (Table S4). Diet treatment had no
281 effect on the difference between cusps (Table S4).

282

283 **Original tooth state**

284 Before the initial CT scan and the beginning of the experimental feeding period, the animals,
285 whose previous diets were unknown, had been kept for two weeks on a common diet of
286 lucerne hay and lucerne pellets. Nevertheless, the initial CT scan indicated that significant
287 differences in OR and CSA between the groups had been present before the start of the
288 experiment (with the group to be fed lucerne having higher reliefs and sharper anterior cusps
289 than the other groups in many comparisons), even though animals had been assigned
290 randomly to the groups (Table S5). At the end of the experiment, the results from scoring the
291 final CT scans resembled those of the initial CT scans and those of the skulls, with animals
292 on lucerne having higher relief and sharper cusps than the other groups (Table 3). In pair-
293 wise comparisons, differences between the initial and final CT scores were never significant
294 for OR, but significant differences occurred for CSA for all molars, the lower premolars, the
295 upper M2 and the lower p2, and for CSP in the upper M1 (Table 4). Diet had a significant
296 effect on the difference in mesowear score between the initial and final CT scans, indicating
297 that the L diet had the most distinct (negative) score change, towards higher OR and sharper
298 CS, while GR changed towards lower OR and blunter CS (Table 4; displayed for all molars
299 in Fig. 4 and individual teeth in Fig. 5).

300

301 **DISCUSSION**

302 The key results of this study show that documenting effects corresponding to current
303 mesowear theory was possible in goats, but that these effects appear to be very small. Our
304 findings further suggest that in ruminants like goats, mesowear signals may develop at a
305 slower rate than previously assumed.

306

307 **Limitations of study design and method**

308 Upon arrival, the animals' previous diets and exact ages were unknown, and their teeth were
309 in various conditions. Because crown height is one of the parameters that influences
310 mesowear score stability within a species (Rivals et al., 2007), it was important to record
311 tooth state before the beginning of the feeding experiment. To dampen this effect, animals
312 could have been sorted into more homogenous groups based on age and overall tooth wear
313 state after the initial CT scan. Alternatively, the animals could first have been kept for an
314 extensive period of time (given our results, > 6 months), on a common diet, though this was
315 beyond our logistical capacities.

316 Secondly, the experimental diets were provided predominantly in pelleted form.
317 Supplying the animals with solely forage-based diets could have been a better representation
318 of the effect of natural forages. However, the logistics of applying external abrasives
319 consistently to this type of diet over long periods of time was considered impractical, and
320 using different natural forages would automatically have introduced other sources of bias,
321 e.g. differences in digestible energy content between forages as well as individual selectivity
322 or inter-group disparity. The pelleted experimental diets used for the present study were
323 specifically designed to be isocaloric and isonitrogenic, in order to avoid differences in the
324 total amount ingested.

325 Another consideration is the original statement by Fortelius and Solounias (2000), that
326 the ideal sample size for mesowear scoring should be between 10 and 30 individuals. For a
327 preliminary study, such a large number of animals per diet group would have been excessive
328 and unethical. Furthermore, given our results, it appears doubtful that a higher sample size
329 would have demonstrated a larger effect, but only a more significant one.

330 Finally, combining the OR and CS scores into a single variable did not provide more
331 insight into diet separation. This may be a convenient procedure for further statistical testing
332 of mesowear in relation to other factors, but should not be considered an improvement of the
333 informative value of the score.

334

335

336 **Mesowear methodology**

337 According to the original mesowear technique, the sharper of two molar cusps is often used
338 to provide the final tooth score. In the present study, both cusps were scored and these scores
339 were subjected to statistical testing. Thus, the results of our study on goats support the
340 suggestion by Fortelius and Solounias (2000) that there is generally no difference between
341 the sharpness of the anterior and posterior cusps within the same molar, at least for measures
342 performed on the skulls.

343 Originally, the mesowear technique scored only the upper M2 "for simplicity"
344 (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000). Yet, the second molar could be the ideal tooth to represent
345 the mesowear signal, as the first molar erupts first and endures more wear, while the third
346 molar erupts later on and may not have been fully subjected to wear yet. Our results indicate
347 that of all individual teeth investigated, the second molar showed changes closest to our
348 expectations at statistical significance (in four out of six individual tests in Fig. 5), even
349 though several other teeth, in particular the first and third molar, followed the same trend,
350 albeit less often significantly so.

351 When scoring mesowear on CT scans, the results indicate OR scoring as similar
352 between CT scans and real skulls. Cusp sharpness however is reduced in CT imagery as
353 medical CT scanners are restricted by resolution. The very sharp points are therefore lost at
354 lower resolution, though general relief is conserved (Fig. 6). When results are ranked, diet
355 differences between individuals are maintained and mesowear scoring remains accurate. It
356 should be noted that 3D renderings do not provide an exact representation of the physical
357 teeth and should therefore only be used to make comparisons within individuals, or within an
358 experimental setup. However, the possibility of applying mesowear scoring to 3D
359 reconstructions of teeth based on medical CT imagery allows expanding the use of mesowear
360 from physical animal skulls to 3D scans of live sedated animals, also to observe signal
361 development over time.

362

363 **Magnitude of mesowear change**

364 The most important finding to emerge from this study is that after spending six months on the
365 experimental diet, it was not possible to sort the animals' skulls into correct diet groups based
366 on the mesowear score alone. Even though OR and CS scores showed some significant
367 differences between groups, these differences were of a surprisingly small magnitude (Fig.
368 2). It was only after using the differential scores between first and last CT scans, that testing
369 whether mesowear development followed the predicted theory became possible.

370 Current literature is ambiguous on the exact time period a mesowear signal takes to
371 develop and provides vague estimates at best. To this day, no concrete testing of this duration

372 has been made. Fortelius and Solounias (2000) originally state mesowear as reflecting "*a*
373 *substantial portion of the individual's life in ecological time*", whereas others (Brent Jones
374 and Desantis, 2017; Merceron et al., 2007; Yamada, 2012) describe mesowear as
375 representing an average lifelong diet. Some research has defined mesowear as representing an
376 animals' diet over the few last months or years of its life (Rivals et al., 2007; Ulbricht et al.,
377 2015), with some placing the cap at one year (Loffredo and DeSantis, 2014; Louys et al.,
378 2012), or even weeks to years, depending on tooth wear state (Danowitz et al., 2016). If,
379 according to the present study, mesowear signals resulting from feeding pelleted diets to
380 goats take more than half a year to develop clearly, a resolution allowing to track mid-term
381 diet changes such as seasonal diet switches is to be questioned, at least in ruminants. Though
382 most studies tend to use caution when evoking the timeframe represented by the mesowear
383 signal, it is often combined with microwear to measure diet seasonality (Kaiser and Schulz,
384 2006; Muhlbachler and Solounias, 2006; Rivals et al., 2013). Kubo and Yamada (2014) use
385 the standard deviation of the mesowear score for this purpose. If mesowear takes longer than
386 a season to develop, the relationship between mesowear and seasonality will need to be re-
387 evaluated. However, taxon-specific conditions also need be to considered. For example, as
388 mentioned in the introduction, a mesowear signal in lagomorphs (Fraser and Theodor, 2010;
389 Ulbricht et al., 2015) must develop with 1-2 weeks, given the rate at which cheek tooth tissue
390 is being replaced.

391 The change in mesowear score in our study was always less than one mesowear unit
392 and, more often, closer to a change of 0.25. In a very general fashion, one could interpret this
393 as the occlusal relief slightly shifting from high towards high-low and in cusp shape from
394 round towards round-round in animals experiencing abrasion. A change of at least 2
395 mesowear units would be needed to consider animals as having separate diets like browser or
396 grazer, for example. The small shifts in mesowear signal observed over a period of half a
397 year brings into consideration the real resolution of the mesowear signal, and offers the
398 possibility of it being more of a lifetime signal in ruminants rather than only representing the
399 last months of an individual's diet. This in turn could have an impact on paleontological
400 reconstructions and call for reconsideration of those based on mesowear being a seasonal
401 signal.

402

403 **Phytolith effect**

404 The phytolith contents of the experimental diets used in this study are at expected levels
405 based on plant silica content in Hodson et al. (2005). The hardness of phytoliths and whether
406 they notably affect tooth wear is strongly debated (Baker et al., 1959; Damuth and Janis,

407 2011; Lucas et al., 2014; Mainland, 2003; Sanson et al., 2007; Xia et al., 2015). In our
408 experimental setting, diets containing more phytoliths, i.e. grass and rice husks vs. grass or
409 vs. lucerne, caused some abrasive-type wear on ruminant teeth, but the greater change in
410 mesowear (measured as the distance from zero change) was affected by the diet lowest in
411 phytoliths, i.e. lucerne (Fig. 4), suggesting that in our setting, attrition-related sharpening of
412 cusps and deepening valleys was more prominent than abrasion-related blunting of cusps and
413 flattening of valleys. In experiments using the same food with small mammals, tooth wear
414 was not measured by mesowear but by loss of dental tissue via tooth length. In rabbits
415 (Müller et al., 2014) as well as guinea pigs (Müller et al., 2015), when compared within in the
416 same animals (in these animals, repeated measures are logistically possible), the GR diet led
417 to shorter teeth than the G or L diets.

418 The difference in dietary phytolith content was also hypothesized (though not proven)
419 to be the cause of observed lower mesowear scores in captive giraffe (*Giraffa*
420 *camelopardalis*) (Clauss et al., 2007), browsing ruminants (Kaiser et al., 2009) and black
421 rhinoceros (*Diceros bicornis*, a browser) (Taylor et al., 2014). These animals putatively
422 receive more grass-related products in captivity than normal for their typically dicot-
423 dominated diets, resulting in abnormally worn teeth. Our observations in this study concur
424 with the previous assumptions that phytolith rich diets induce higher rates of dental tissue
425 loss and lead to rounded, lower mesowear profiles, but more prominently emphasize the
426 putative effect of attrition-related change in dental morphology towards sharper teeth.

427

428 **Grit (sand) effect**

429 The size of external grit as abrasive dietary particles may be an important factor when
430 considering their effect on mesowear. Large-grained sand, similar to that added to the diets in
431 the present study, tends to cause great amounts of wear in cases such as soil ingestion;
432 documented in agricultural (Healy, 1965; Ludwig et al., 1966) and zoo (Martin Jurado et al.,
433 2008) settings. Another illustration of the effect of external abrasives is the case of the
434 pronghorn antelope (*Antilocapra americana*), an antilocaprid seen as an outlier to the known
435 association between grazing and hypsodonty (Janis and Fortelius, 1988). Both hypsodont
436 teeth, usually related to grazing animals and their highly abrasive diet, and a high/sharp
437 mesowear profile, indicating a browser diet, are present in the pronghorn (Damuth and Janis,
438 2011; Fortelius and Solounias, 2000; Rivals and Semprebon, 2006; Semprebon and Rivals,
439 2007). As these animals consume only small amounts of grass, one hypothesis for the high
440 hypsodonty and high mesowear score recorded in this species is that their open environment
441 and close-ground feeding behaviour results in the ingestion of large amounts of external

442 abrasives in the form of dust (Damuth and Janis, 2011), therefore mandating high-crowned
443 teeth. Due to the lack of deviation from the typical browser mesowear signal in the pronghorn
444 however, Kaiser et al. (2013) hypothesized that intrinsic abrasives (phytoliths) determine
445 facet development (mesowear appearance), while external abrasives in the form of small
446 airborne dust particles could cause uniform loss of dental tissue, shortening the teeth all while
447 conserving the mesowear pattern. Experimental studies with external abrasives of a variety of
448 size classes are required to further our understanding of the role of grit and dust.

449 In the present study, when adding large amounts of coarse abrasives (sand) to the
450 experimental diet, the change in mesowear signal between start and end was similar to, or
451 lower than, that of the same diet without sand, contrary to our expectations. Additionally, in a
452 controlled microwear study on sheep, where mesowear was not determined, Merceron et al.
453 (2016) found a dietary signal difference in dental microwear texture between monocot and
454 dicot roughage, but no relevant additional signal change when dust was added to these diets.
455 In all likelihood, the key to these differences lies in the way the abrasives (phytoliths vs. sand
456 or dust) are embedded in the matrix of the food bolus. Ruminants process food repeatedly
457 through the chewing and regurgitation of cud (Gordon, 1968). While phytoliths are
458 embedded in the plant material, added/exogenous grit may possibly be "washed off" and
459 settle in the rumen, resulting in a less abrasive bolus at regurgitation, which would limit the
460 effects of external abrasives on the teeth (Dittmann et al., 2017; Janis et al., 2010). This
461 "washing" mechanism could explain the lack of effect of sand in goats (present study) and of
462 dust in sheep (Merceron et al., 2016), and provide a reason for why low chewing intensity at
463 ingestion, as compared to rumination, might be adaptive in ruminants (Dittmann et al., 2017).
464 Moreover, the observation that effects on the sand diet appeared even somewhat lower than
465 the same diet without sand could suggest that the goats chewed the sand-containing diet less
466 intensely at ingestion. In humans, reduced chewing intensity due to the presence of external
467 abrasives has been documented in a chewing gum study (Prinz, 2004). Whether herbivores,
468 ruminant or not, adjust chewing intensity based on the sensory perception of external
469 abrasives in the ingesta, while appearing probable, remains to be investigated.

470 This hypothesis further suggests that we expect a distinct difference in the effect of
471 external abrasives on tooth wear between ruminant and non-ruminant herbivores. Indeed,
472 results of the same diets used in (non-ruminant) rabbits and guinea pigs (Müller et al., 2014;
473 Müller et al., 2015) indicate a dramatic effect of the external abrasives. Not only did the
474 added-sand diet lead to the relatively shortest cheek teeth and highest wear (and highest
475 growth rates of the hypselodont cheek teeth), but also to abnormal dental morphology. This
476 reflects the fact that these animals are obliged to chew intensively at ingestion, lacking the

477 option of washing off external abrasives. Additionally, in an in-vitro study (Karme et al.,
478 2016) again using the same experimental diets, horse teeth were subjected to standardized
479 chewing in a mechanical chewing machine. Actual tooth wear was measured by observing
480 volume loss via micro-CT, and results showed that the GRS diet led to the largest amount of
481 tissue loss, mimicking the results of the same diet in non-ruminants. Overall, these results
482 indicate that a diet containing sand affected the teeth of two non-ruminant species but did not
483 have a comparable effect on the teeth of a ruminant. While we cannot rule out body size
484 effects, these results highlight the different mechanisms adopted throughout species in order
485 to avoid tooth wear.

486

487 **CONCLUSIONS**

488 The results of this preliminary study infer that in goats, half a year is not enough time for a
489 mesowear signal to develop conclusively. Accordingly, the lack of a clear distinction
490 between diets after using solely controlled diets for six months suggests that in ruminants, the
491 mesowear signal should possibly be considered more as a lifetime or, possibly, depending on
492 future results, an annual rather than seasonal signal.

493 The use of CT-based 3D reconstructions for tracing the development of the mesowear
494 signal was an important factor in this study, and further application of this technique could
495 help increase our understanding of mesowear signal development. Similar study designs,
496 including diets with varying sizes and concentrations of grit particles and longer experimental
497 periods, are recommended in order to obtain a solid functional understanding of mesowear-
498 based dietary reconstructions.

499 Some of the expected effects on mesowear were found, but only once differences
500 between initial and final mesowear scores were observed, a technique difficult to apply in
501 specimens most often subject to mesowear, i.e. fossil or extant-but-deceased specimens. The
502 observed changes indicate, unexpectedly, that diets richer in phytoliths and sand caused less
503 change in mesowear on ruminant teeth than a diet deplete of abrasives (which led to
504 higher/sharper mesowear). Also unexpectedly, the diet with added sand caused mesowear
505 differences similar to those of the same diet without sand, suggesting the possibility that in
506 ruminants, food may be "washed" free of external abrasives when being prepared in the
507 rumen for regurgitation. Thus, the findings also emphasize the relevance of internal abrasives
508 (phytoliths) for the adaptive acquisition of hypsodont molars in ruminants. In the absence of
509 grit effects, internal abrasives may play a more important role in enforcing adaptive
510 responses against tooth wear in ruminants than previously acknowledged.

511

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518
519 **Competing interests**

520 The authors declare no competing or financial interests.

521
522 **Author contributions**

523 TMK, DWHM, PRK, MC and JMH designed the study; DWHM and MC performed the animal experiment;
524 PRK supervised the CT scanning; JH supervised the nutritional analyses; NLA performed the mesowear scoring
525 of CT scans and skulls under supervision of ESK, TMK and DEW; NLA and MC analyzed the data and drafted
526 the first version of the manuscript which then received input by all other co-authors.

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533
534 **Supplementary Information**

535 Supplementary information available online as an excel file, and Fig. S1 and Tables S1-5 as a PDF file.

536
537 **References**

- 538 **Baker, G., Jones, L. H. P. and Wardrop, I. D.** (1959). Cause of wear in sheep's
539 teeth. *Nature* **184**, 1583-1584.
- 540 **Brent Jones, D. and Desantis, L. R. G.** (2017). Dietary ecology of ungulates from
541 the La Brea tar pits in southern California: A multi-proxy approach. *Palaeogeogr*
542 *Palaeoclimatol Palaeoecol* **466**, 110-127.
- 543 **Butler, K., Louys, J. and Travouillon, K.** (2014). Extending dental mesowear
544 analyses to Australian marsupials, with applications to six Plio-Pleistocene kangaroos from
545 southeast Queensland. *Palaeogeogr Palaeoclimatol Palaeoecol* **408**, 11-25.
- 546 **Clauss, M., Franz-Odenaal, T. A., Brasch, J., Castell, J. C. and Kaiser, T.**
547 (2007). Tooth wear in captive giraffes (*Giraffa camelopardalis*): mesowear analysis classifies
548 free-ranging specimens as browsers but captive ones as grazers. *J Zoo Wildl Med* **38**, 433-45.
- 549 **Croft, D. A. and Weinstein, D.** (2008). The first application of the mesowear method
550 to endemic South American ungulates (Notoungulata). *Palaeogeogr Palaeoclimatol*
551 *Palaeoecol* **269**, 103-114.
- 552 **Damuth, J. and Janis, C. M.** (2011). On the relationship between hypsodonty and
553 feeding ecology in ungulate mammals, and its utility in palaeoecology. *Biol. Rev.* **86**, 733-
554 758.

555 **Danowitz, M., Hou, S., Mhlbachler, M., Hastings, V. and Solounias, N.** (2016). A
556 combined-mesowear analysis of late Miocene giraffids from North Chinese and Greek
557 localities of the Pikermian Biome. *Palaeogeogr Palaeoclimatol Palaeoecol* **449**, 194-204.

558 **Dittmann, M. T., Kreuzer, M., Runge, U. and Clauss, M.** (2017). Ingestive
559 mastication in horses resembles rumination but not ingestive mastication in cattle and camels.
560 *JEZ-A* **327**, 98-109.

561 **Fortelius, M. and Solounias, N.** (2000). Functional characterization of ungulate
562 molars using the abrasion-attrition wear gradient: a new method for reconstructing paleodiets.
563 *Am Mus Novit*, 1-36.

564 **Franz-Odendaal, T. A. and Kaiser, T. M.** (2003). Differential mesowear in the
565 maxillary and mandibular cheek dentition of some ruminants (Artiodactyla). *Ann. Zool. Fenn.*
566 **40**, 395-410.

567 **Fraser, D. and Theodor, J. M.** (2010). The use of gross dental wear in dietary
568 studies of extinct lagomorphs. *J. Palaeontol.* **84**, 720-729.

569 **Gordon, J. G.** (1968). Rumination and its significance. In *World Review of Nutrition*
570 *and Dietetics*, vol. 9, pp. 251-273: Karger Publishers.

571 **Healy, W. B.** (1965). Ingestion of soil by sheep. *Soil Bureau D. S. I. R., Lower Hutt*,
572 109-120.

573 **Hodson, M. J., White, P. J., Mead, A. and Broadley, M. R.** (2005). Phylogenetic
574 variation in the silicon composition of plants. *Ann Bot* **96**, 1027-1046.

575 **Hummel, J., Findeisen, E., Südekum, K.-H., Ruf, I., Kaiser, T. M., Bucher, M.,**
576 **Clauss, M. and Codron, D.** (2011). Another one bites the dust: faecal silica levels in large
577 herbivores correlate with high-crowned teeth. *Proc. Royal Soc. Lond* **278**, 1742-1747.

578 **Janis, C. M., Constable, E. C., Houpt, K. A., Streich, W. J. and Clauss, M.**
579 (2010). Comparative ingestive mastication in domestic horses and cattle: a pilot investigation.
580 *J. Anim. Physiol. Anim. Nutr.* **94**, e402-e409.

581 **Janis, C. M. and Fortelius, M.** (1988). On the means whereby mammals achieve
582 increased functional durability of their dentitions, with special reference to limiting factors.
583 *Biol Rev* **63**, 197-230.

584 **Kaiser, T. M.** (2000). Tooth mesowear analysis on hippotherium primigenium from
585 the Vallesian Dinotheriensande (Germany). *Carolinea - Beitr. naturkd. Forsch.*
586 *Südwestdeutschland* **58**, 103-114.

587 **Kaiser, T. M., Brasch, J., Castell, J. C., Schulz, E. and Clauss, M.** (2009). Tooth
588 wear in captive wild ruminant species differs from that of free-ranging conspecifics.
589 *Mammalian Biology - Zeitschrift für Säugetierkunde* **74**, 425-437.

590 **Kaiser, T. M. and Fortelius, M.** (2003). Differential mesowear in occluding upper
591 and lower molars: opening mesowear analysis for lower molars and premolars in hypsodont
592 horses. *J Morphol* **258**, 67-83.

593 **Kaiser, T. M., Müller, D. W. H., Fortelius, M., Schulz, E., Codron, D. and Clauss,**
594 **M.** (2013). Hypsodonty and tooth facet development in relation to diet and habitat in
595 herbivorous ungulates: implications for understanding tooth wear. *Mamm Rev* **43**, 34-46.

596 **Kaiser, T. M. and Schulz, E.** (2006). Tooth wear gradients in zebras as an
597 environmental proxy—a pilot study. *Mitteilungen aus dem Hamburgischen Zoologischen*
598 *Museum und Institut* **103**, 187-210.

599 **Kaiser, T. M. and Solounias, N.** (2003). Extending the tooth mesowear method to
600 extinct and extant equids. *Geodiversitas* **25**, 321-345.

601 **Karme, A., Rannikko, J., Kallonen, A., Clauss, M. and Fortelius, M.** (2016).
602 Mechanical modelling of tooth wear. *J R Soc Interface* **13**, 20160399.

603 **Kropacheva, Y. E., Sibiryakov, P. A., Smirnov, N. G. and Zыkov, S. V.** (2017).
604 Variants of tooth mesowear in *Microtus* voles as indicators of food hardness and
605 abrasiveness. *Russian Journal of Ecology* **48**, 73-80.

606 **Kubo, M. O. and Yamada, E.** (2014). The inter-relationship between dietary and
607 environmental properties and tooth wear: comparisons of mesowear, molar wear rate, and
608 hypsodonty index of extant sika deer populations. *PloS one* **9**.

609 **Loffredo, L. F. and DeSantis, L. R.** (2014). Cautionary lessons from assessing
610 dental mesowear observer variability and integrating paleoecological proxies of an extreme
611 generalist *Cormohipparion emsliei*. *Palaeogeogr Palaeoclimatol Palaeoecol* **395**, 42-52.

612 **Louys, J., Ditchfield, P., Meloro, C., Elton, S. and Bishop, L. C.** (2012). Stable
613 isotopes provide independent support for the use of mesowear variables for inferring diets in
614 African antelopes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences* **279**,
615 4441-4446.

616 **Lucas, P. W., Van Casteren, A., Al-Fadhlah, K., Almusallam, A. S., Henry, A.**
617 **G., Michael, S., Watzke, J., Reed, D. A., Diekwisch, T. G., Strait, D. S. et al.** (2014). The
618 role of dust, grit and phytoliths in tooth wear. *Ann. Zool. Fenn.* **51**, 143-152.

619 **Ludwig, T. G., Healy, W. B. and Cutress, T. W.** (1966). Wear of sheep's teeth: III.
620 Seasonal variation in wear and ingested soil. *New Zeal J Agr Res* **9**, 157-164.

621 **Mainland, I. L.** (2003). Dental microwear in grazing and browsing Gotland sheep
622 (*Ovis aries*) and its implications for dietary reconstruction. *J Archaeol Sci* **30**, 1513-1527.

623 **Martin Jurado, O., Clauss, M. and Hatt, J.-M.** (2008). Irregular tooth wear and
624 longevity in captive wild ruminants: a pilot survey of necropsy reports. *J. Zoo Wildl. Med.*
625 **39**, 69-75.

626 **Merceron, G., Ramdarshan, A., Blondel, C., Boisserie, J. R., Brunetiere, N.,**
627 **Francisco, A., Gautier, D., Milhet, X., Novello, A. and Pret, D.** (2016). Untangling the
628 environmental from the dietary: dust does not matter. *Proc. R. Soc. B* **283**, 20161032.

629 **Merceron, G., Schulz, E., Kordos, L. and Kaiser, T. M.** (2007). Paleoenvironment
630 of *Dryopithecus brancoi* at Rudabánya, Hungary: evidence from dental meso- and micro-wear
631 analyses of large vegetarian mammals. *J Hum Evol* **53**, 331-349.

632 **Mihlbachler, M. C., Rivals, F., Solounias, N. and Semperebon, G. M.** (2011).
633 Dietary change and evolution of horses in North America. *Science* **331**, 1178-1181.

634 **Mihlbachler, M. C. and Solounias, N.** (2006). Coevolution of tooth crown height
635 and diet in oreodonts (*Merycoidodontidae*, Artiodactyla) examined with phylogenetically
636 independent contrasts. *J. Mamm. Evol.* **13**, 11-36.

637 **Müller, J., Clauss, M., Codron, D., Schulz, E., Hummel, J., Fortelius, M.,**
638 **Kircher, P. and Hatt, J.-M.** (2014). Growth and wear of incisor and cheek teeth in domestic
639 rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) fed diets of different abrasiveness. *JEZ-A* **321**, 283-298.

640 **Müller, J., Clauss, M., Codron, D., Schulz, E., Hummel, J., Kircher, P. and Hatt,**
641 **J.-M.** (2015). Tooth length and incisal wear and growth in guinea pigs (*Cavia porcellus*) fed
642 diets of different abrasiveness. *J Anim Physiol Anim Nutr* **99**, 591-604.

643 **Prinz, J. F.** (2004). Abrasives in foods and their effect on intra - oral processing: a
644 two - colour chewing gum study. *Journal of Oral Rehabilitation* **31**, 968-971.

645 **Rivals, F., Mihlbachler, M. C. and Solounias, N.** (2007). Effect of ontogenetic-age
646 distribution in fossil and modern samples on the interpretation of ungulate paleodiets using
647 the mesowear method. *J Vert Paleo* **27**, 763-767.

648 **Rivals, F., Rindel, D. and Belardi, J. B.** (2013). Dietary ecology of extant guanaco
649 (*Lama guanicoe*) from Southern Patagonia: seasonal leaf browsing and its archaeological
650 implications. *J Archaeol Sci* **40**, 2971-2980.

651 **Rivals, F. and Semperebon, G. M.** (2006). A comparison of the dietary habits of a
652 large sample of the Pleistocene pronghorn *Stockoceros onusrosagris* from the Papago Springs
653 Cave in Arizona to the modern *Antilocapra americana*. *J Vert Paleo* **26**, 495-500.

654 **Saarinen, J. and Karme, A.** (2017). Tooth wear and diets of extant and fossil
655 xenarthrans (*Mammalia, Xenarthra*) – Applying a new mesowear approach. *Palaeogeogr*
656 *Palaeoclimatol Palaeoecol* **476**, 42-54.

657 **Saarinen, J., Karme, A., Cerling, T., Uno, K., Säilä, L., Kasiki, S., Ngene, S.,**
658 **Obari, T., Mbua, E. and Manthi, F. K.** (2015). A new tooth wear-based dietary analysis
659 method for proboscidea (*Mammalia*). *J Vert Paleo* **35**.
660 **Sanson, G. D., Kerr, S. A. and Gross, K. A.** (2007). Do silica phytoliths really wear
661 mammalian teeth? *J Archaeol Sci* **34**, 526-531.
662 **Schulz, E., Fahlke, J. M., Merceron, G. and Kaiser, T. M.** (2007). Feeding ecology
663 of the Chalicotheriidae. Results from dental micro- and mesowear analyses. *Verhandlungen*
664 *des Naturwissenschaftlichen Vereins in Hamburg* **43**, 5-32.
665 **Schulz, E., Fraas, S., Kaiser, T. M., Cunningham, P. L., Ismail, K. and Wronski,**
666 **T.** (2013). Food preferences and tooth wear in the sand gazelle (*Gazella marica*). *Mamm.*
667 *Biol.* **78**, 55-62.
668 **Semprebon, G. M. and Rivals, F.** (2007). Was grass more prevalent in the
669 pronghorn past? An assessment of the dietary adaptations of Miocene to recent
670 Antilocapridae (*Mammalia: Artiodactyla*). *Palaeogeogr Palaeoclimatol Palaeoecol* **253**,
671 332-347.
672 **Solounias, N., Tariq, M., Hou, S., Danowitz, M. and Harrison, M.** (2014). A new
673 method of tooth mesowear and a test of it on domestic goats. *Annales Zoologici Fennici* **51**,
674 111-118.
675 **Taylor, L. A., Kaiser, T. M., Schwitzer, C., Müller, D. W. H., Codron, D., Clauss,**
676 **M. and Schulz, E.** (2013). Detecting inter-cusp and inter-tooth wear patterns in
677 Rhinocerotids. *PloS one* **8**.
678 **Taylor, L. A., Müller, D. W. H., Schwitzer, C., Kaiser, T. M., Castell, J. C.,**
679 **Clauss, M. and Schulz - Kornas, E.** (2016). Comparative analyses of tooth wear in free -
680 ranging and captive wild equids. *Equine Vet J* **48**, 240-245.
681 **Taylor, L. A., Müller, D. W. H., Schwitzer, C., Kaiser, T. M., Codron, D., Schulz,**
682 **E. and Clauss, M.** (2014). Tooth wear in captive rhinoceroses (*Diceros, Rhinoceros,*
683 *Ceratotherium: Perissodactyla*) differs from that of free-ranging conspecifics. *Contrib Zool*
684 **83**, 107-117.
685 **Ulbricht, A., Maul, L. C. and Schulz, E.** (2015). Can mesowear analysis be applied
686 to small mammals? A pilot-study on leporines and murines. *Mamm. Biol.* **80**, 14-20.
687 **Winkler, D. E. and Kaiser, T. M.** (2011). A case study of seasonal, sexual and
688 ontogenetic divergence in the feeding behaviour of the moose (*Alces alces*, Linné, 1758).
689 *Verhandlungen des Naturwissenschaftlichen Vereins Hamburg* **46**, 331-348.
690 **Wronski, T. and Schulz-Kornas, E.** (2015). The Farasan gazelle - a frugivorous
691 browser in an arid environment? *Mamm. Biol.* **80**, 87-95.
692 **Xia, J., Zheng, J., Huang, D., Tian, Z. R., Chen, L., Zhou, Z., Ungar, P. S. and**
693 **Qian, L.** (2015). New model to explain tooth wear with implications for microwear
694 formation and diet reconstruction. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* **112**, 10669-10672.
695 **Yamada, E.** (2012). Mesowear analysis of the Japanese Sika Deer (*Cervus nippon*) in
696 different food habits: its limitations and applicability. *Mammal Study* **37**, 93-103.
697

698 **Table 1. Effect of different diets on teeth of goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) (n=28) fed**
 699 **four pelleted diets of different abrasiveness for six months, quantified by mesowear**
 700 **occlusal relief and cusp shape of the anterior and posterior cusp on skulls at the end of**
 701 **the experiment.**

Tooth	Occlusal relief skull		Cusp shape anterior skull		Cusp shape posterior skull	
	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>
all teeth	<0.001	L>G,GR,GRS	<0.001	L>G,GRS; GR>GRS		
all premolars	<0.001	L>G,GR,GRS; GR>GRS	<0.001	L>G,GRS		
all molars	<0.001	L>G,GR,GRS	0.003	L,GR>GRS	0.034	L>GRS
upper premolars	<0.001	L>G,GRS	0.34	-		
lower premolars	<0.001	L,GR>GRS	<0.001	L>G,GRS		
upper molars	0.015	L>GR	0.022	GR>GRS	0.013	L>GR,GRS
lower molars	0.002	L>G,GR	0.057	-	0.549	-
txP2	0.021	L>GRS	0.351	-		
txP3	0.061	-	0.677	-		
txP4	0.136	-	0.587	-		
txM1	0.443	-	0.025	G<GR	0.199	-
txM2	0.413	-	0.225	-	0.069	-
txM3	0.293	-	0.750	-	0.741	-
tmP2	0.013	L>GRS	0.073	-		
tmP3	0.002	L>G,GRS	0.008	L>G,GRS		
tmP4	0.339	-	0.276	-		
tmM1	0.001	L>G,GR3	0.888	-	0.901	-
tmM2	0.064	-	0.184	-	0.586	-
tmM3	0.531	-	0.143	-	0.788	-

702 *L lucerne (n=7), G grass (n=7), GR grass/rice husks (n=7), GRS grass/rice husks/sand (n=7), tx maxillary, tm mandibular.*
 703 *General Linear Models performed on ranked data. Tests made for all teeth combined, subcategories and individual teeth.*
 704

705 **Table 2. Significance of differences of mesowear scores of teeth of goats (*Capra aegagrus***
706 ***hircus*) (n=28) fed four pelleted diets of different abrasiveness for six months, from CT**
707 **scans taken at the end of the experiment and on macerated skulls representing the same**
708 **time point, as well as the effect of diet on this difference for occlusal relief (OR),**
709 **anterior cusp shape (CSA), posterior cusp shape (CSP).**

Tooth	Difference between skull and CT			Effect of diet on the difference					
	OR	CSA	CSP	OR	CSA		CSP		<i>post hoc</i>
	<i>p</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>	<i>p</i>	
all teeth	0.257	<0.001	<0.001	0.241	-	0.049	GR>GRS		
all premolars	0.231	<0.001	-	0.068	-	0.214	-		
all molars	0.649	<0.001	<0.001	0.312	-	0.186	-	0.751	-
upper premolars	0.842	0.001	-	0.039	-	0.781	-		
lower premolars	0.312	<0.001	-	0.007	GR>GRS	0.044	GR>GRS		
upper molars	0.144	<0.001	<0.001	0.537	-	0.025	GR>GRS	0.246	-
lower molars	0.692	0.008	0.030	0.007	L,G<GRS	0.924	-	0.786	-
txP2	0.783	0.425	-	0.958	-	0.647	-		
txP3	0.864	0.035	-	0.411	-	0.866	-		
txP4	0.847	0.007	-	0.505	-	0.920	-		
txM1	0.810	0.108	0.001	0.494	-	0.211	-	0.721	-
txM2	0.336	0.003	<0.001	0.542	-	0.321	-	0.506	-
txM3	0.258	0.015	<0.001	0.681	-	0.582	-	0.248	-
tmP2	0.864	0.153	-	0.643	-	0.828	-		
tmP3	0.105	<0.001	-	0.701	-	0.504	-		
tmP4	0.449	0.036	-	0.091	-	0.115	-		
tmM1	0.321	0.040	0.060	0.344	-	0.764	-	0.910	-
tmM2	0.621	0.333	0.955	0.056	-	0.856	-	0.394	-
tmM3	0.653	0.102	0.025	0.523	-	0.819	-	0.751	-

710 *Comparisons between skulls and CTs by Wilcoxon signed-rank tests for paired samples. Effect of diet (L lucerne (n=7), G*
711 *grass (n=7), GR grass/rice husks (n=7), GRS grass/rice husks/sand (n=7)) tested by General Linear Models performed on*
712 *ranked data. tx maxillary; tm mandibular. Tests made for all teeth combined, subcategories and individual teeth.*

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714 **Table 3. Significance of differences in the final scores on teeth of goats (*Capra aegagrus***
715 ***hircus*) (n=28) fed four pelleted diets of different abrasiveness for six months, quantified**
716 **by mesowear occlusal relief and cusp shape of the anterior and posterior cusp on CTs at**
717 **the end of the experiment (corresponding in time point to the scores on the skulls tested**
718 **in Table 1).**

Tooth	Occlusal relief final CT		Cusp shape anterior final CT		Cusp shape posterior final CT	
	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>
all teeth	<0.001	L>G,GR,GRS	<0.001	L>G,GR,GRS		
all premolars	<0.001	L>G,GR,GRS	0.001	L>G,GR,GRS		
all molars	<0.001	L>G,GR,GRS	0.003	L>G,GR,GRS	0.045	L>GR
upper premolars	<0.001	L>G,GR,GRS	0.052	-		
lower premolars	0.001	L>GR,GRS	0.003	L>GR		
upper molars	0.103	-	0.034	L>GR	0.502	-
lower molars	<0.001	L>GR,GRS	0.14	-	0.074	-
txP2	0.035	L>GRS	0.078	-		
txP3	0.021	L>G	0.368	-		
txP4	0.118	-	0.867	-		
txM1	0.292	-	0.199	-	0.675	-
txM2	0.706	-	0.396	-	0.488	-
txM3	0.195	-	0.237	-	0.271	-
tmP2	0.019	L>GRS, L>GR	0.061	-		
tmP3	0.027	L>GRS	0.039	-		
tmP4	0.306	-	0.094	-		
tmM1	0.103	-	0.132	-	0.268	-
tmM2	0.004	L>GR,GRS	0.445	-	0.327	-
tmM3	0.176	-	0.628	-	0.514	-

719 *L lucerne (n=7), G grass (n=7), GR grass/rice husks (n=7), GRS grass/rice husks/sand (n=7), tx maxillary, tm mandibular.*

720 *General Linear Models performed on ranked data. Tests made for all teeth combined, subcategories and individual teeth.*

721

722 **Table 4. Significance of differences of mesowear scores of teeth of goats (*Capra aegagrus***
723 ***hircus*) (n=28) fed four pelleted diets of different abrasiveness for six months, from CT**
724 **scans taken at the beginning and end of the experiment, as well as the effect of diet on**
725 **this difference for occlusal relief (OR), anterior cusp shape (CSA), posterior cusp shape**
726 **(CSP).**

Tooth	Difference between			Effect of diet on the difference					
	initial and final CT			OR		CSA		CSP	
	OR	CSA	CSP	OR	CSA	CSP	OR	CSA	CSP
	<i>p</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>post hoc</i>
all teeth	0.231	0.568	0.651	<0.001	L<G,GR,GRS	0.001	L<GR,GRS		
all premolars	0.864	0.121	-	0.004	L<G	0.268	-		
all molars	0.089	0.030	0.651	<0.001	L,G<GR,GRS	<0.001	L<G,GR,GRS G<GR	<0.001	L<GR,GRS GR<GRS
upper premolars	0.644	0.508	-	0.006	L<G	0.139	-		
lower premolars	0.101	0.023	-	0.395	-	0.490	-		
upper molars	0.830	0.142	0.654	0.116	-	<0.001	L<GR,GRS	0.010	L<GR
lower molars	0.445	0.439	0.885	<0.001	L,G<GR,GRS	<0.001	L<GR,GRS	0.001	L<GR
txP2	0.119	0.197	-	0.052	L<G	0.044	-		
txP3	0.252	0.891	-	0.242	-	0.187	-		
txP4	0.858	0.987	-	0.513	-	0.233	-		
txM1	0.626	0.839	0.036	0.420	-	0.181	-	0.044	L<GRS
txM2	0.322	0.027	0.703	0.583	-	0.008	L<GR	0.010	L<GR
txM3	0.176	0.111	0.073	0.162	-	0.038	L<GR	0.921	-
tmP2	0.182	0.008	-	0.258	-	0.019	L>GR		
tmP3	0.364	0.976	-	0.084	-	0.650	-		
tmP4	0.529	0.920	-	0.467	-	0.848	-		
tmM1	0.386	0.508	0.386	0.117	-	0.167	-	0.013	L<GR
tmM2	1.000	0.955	0.396	0.003	L,G<GR	0.003	L<GR	0.343	-
tmM3	0.527	0.136	0.628	0.052	-	0.342	-	0.328	-

727 *Comparisons between initial and final CTs by Wilcoxon signed-rank tests for paired samples. Effect of diet (L lucerne (n=7),*
728 *G grass (n=7), GR grass/rice husks (n=7), GRS grass/rice husks/sand (n=7)) tested by General Linear Models performed on*
729 *ranked data. tx maxillary; tm mandibular. Tests made for all teeth combined, subcategories and individual teeth.*

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Figure 1. (A) Silica content of different pelleted diets and lucerne (LH) and grass hay (GH), analyzed by ADIA (acid-detergent insoluble ash) supplied for a feeding experiment where goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) (n=28) were fed on four pelleted diets for six months. (B) Analysis of silica content by ADIA (means and standard deviation) on fecal samples produced by goats after consumption of different diets. L lucerne, G grass, GR grass/rice husks, GRS grass/rice husks/sand.

739

740 **Figure 2. Averaged mesowear score of all molars, measured on skulls of goats (*Capra***
 741 ***aegagrus hircus*) (n=28) fed on four pelleted diets of different abrasiveness for six**
 742 **months. A higher mesowear score represents higher and sharper teeth. Each diet is**
 743 **represented according to each of the three scoring parameters; OR occlusal relief, CSA**
 744 **anterior cusp shape, CSP posterior cusp shape. Letters above SD error bars represent**
 745 **significance between diets, within score groups. L lucerne (n=7), G grass (n=7), GR**
 746 **grass/rice husks (n=7), GRS grass/rice husks/sand (n=7).**

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749 **Figure 3. Difference between the averaged mesowear scores calculated for mesowear**
 750 **variables, taken post-mortem on CT images and skulls of goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*)**
 751 **(n=28) fed on four pelleted diets of different abrasiveness for six months. OR occlusal**

752 relief, CSA anterior cusp shape, CSP posterior cusp shape. Distribution of OR differences
 753 showed a mild positive skew (95% confidence interval for skewness 0.008-0.400) and
 754 positive kurtosis (95%CI kurtosis: 0.870-1.654) with a median of 0 and a mean of 0.05.

755 Distribution of CSA differences showed no skew (95%CI: -0.118-0.290) and mild positive
 756 kurtosis (95%CI: 0.479-1.291) with a median of 0 and a mean of 0.38. Distribution of CSP
 757 showed no skew (95%CI: -0.464-0.116) and no kurtosis (95%CI: -0.397-0.759) with a
 758 median of 1 and a mean of 0.59.

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761 **Figure 4. Averaged score difference between the initial and final CT scan, for all molars**
 762 **of goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) (n=28) fed four pelleted diets of different abrasiveness**
 763 **for six months.** Each diet is represented according to each of the three scoring parameters;
 764 OR occlusal relief, CSA anterior cusp shape, CSP posterior cusp shape. Letters above SD
 765 error bars represent significance between diets, within groups. A negative difference indicates
 766 that OR became higher, and CS sharper, during the experiment. L lucerne (n=7), G grass
 767 (n=7), GR grass/rice husks (n=7), GRS grass/rice husks/sand (n=7).

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769 **Figure 5. Averaged score difference between the initial and final CT scan, scored**
 770 **individually for all teeth of goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) (n=28) fed four pelleted diets**
 771 **of different abrasiveness for six months. Letters above SD error bars represent significance**
 772 **between diets, within the respective tooth (Table 4). A negative difference indicates that**
 773 **occlusal relief became higher, and cusp shape sharper, during the experiment. (A) Occlusal**
 774 **relief change maxilla, (B) Occlusal relief change mandible, (C) Anterior cusp shape change**
 775 **maxilla, (D) Anterior cusp shape change mandible, (E) Posterior cusp shape change maxilla,**
 776 **(F) Posterior cusp shape change mandible. L lucerne (n=7), G grass (n=7), GR grass/rice**
 777 **husks (n=7), GRS grass/rice husks/sand (n=7).**

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Figure 6. CT and digital images of the same specimen and position on the upper right tooth row, taken on goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) fed on four pelleted diets of different abrasiveness for six months. (A) Lucerne diet (specimen ID: 13), (B) grass diet (specimen ID: 3), (C) grass-rice diet (specimen ID: 27), (D) grass-rice-sand diet (specimen ID: 4).